

Startup India:Challenges and Opportunities

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ABSTRACT-A scheme which believes in to make the young job creators rather than job seeker as well as emphasis on that one's mindset should not be towards earning money in the initial phase, it should be rather on grabbing and using the opportunities.No doubt that Technology is evolving with the pace faster than ever. This has given birth to various new businesses like E-commerce, Internet Marketing etc. So, there is a great scope of development in such areas. Those who plan to start new business are eligible to apply. In this research paper an attempt has been made over the challenges and opportunities of startup India scheme launched by Govt. of India.

Key words : Startup, Concept, challenges, opportunities, economy

INTRODUCTION- The economy of every country depends on its countrymen. Larger the number of employed or working people, better the economy. The Indian Government realized that Indian people have a potential to work hardly, all they need is a promising start up. Many people dream of starting up their own business but due to financial or other similar issues are unable to do so. So, Indian Government in the leadership of Narendra Modi has decided to offer a gift as a nation wise programme – “Startup India”. “Startup India is a revolutionary scheme that has been started to help the people who wish to start their own business. These people have ideas & capabilities, so the Government will give them support to make sure they can implement their ideas and grow. Success of this scheme will eventually make India a better economy and a strong Nation.” Startup India is an initiative of the Government of India. The event was inaugurated on 16 January 2016 by finance minister Arun Jaitley.

India is a country of many great legends that were famous all over the world because of their work, sharp mind & high skill. Youths in India are very talented, high skilled & full of innovative ideas. But they don't get opportunity due to lack of solid support & proper guidance in right direction. In this way, BJP government launched “START UP INDIA STAND UP INDIA” scheme on 16 January 2016 to help the youth of India to go in right direction using their new & innovative ideas. This scheme was launched to motivate & promote new comers towards business & grow their career as well as economy of the country. This programme is a big start to enable Start ups through financial support so that they can use their innovative ideas in right direction. There are tremendous opportunities for Start up entrepreneurs in India. The key areas are Like Textile, Media, Health Sector, Event

Planner, Tourism, Automobile etc. So there are various opportunities where entrepreneurs can start their Start ups. But along with opportunities there are some challenges also that Start up entrepreneurs may have to face like Infrastructure Deficit in India, Risk Factor and Right Talent Acquisition etc. Despite of these challenges, Government as well Start up entrepreneurs should have to work together to face these challenges & make this programme effective. The study will focus on Start up India scheme, opportunities available under this scheme as well as challenges may have to be faced & suggestions to overcome the challenges so as to make the Start up India programme successful.

Under the Startup India Scheme E- registration will be done, A self certification system will be launched, A dedicated web portal and mobile app will be developed, Arrangement of self certificate based compliance, No inspection during the first 3 years, 80 percent reduction in the application fee of start up patent, Easy exit policy, Inclusion of Credit Guarantee Fund, Relaxation in Income Tax for first three year, Special Arrangement for Female applicants, Introduction of Atal Innovation Mission. Innovation courses will be started for the students

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY-This study is to analyses the start up india . The main objectives of the study can be listed as follows:

- To analyze the concept of STRATUP INDIA.
- To know the need of STARTUP INDIA scheme and coming challenges in the path of STRATUP.
- To study the opportunities for startup scheme in Indian scenario.
- To study the opportunities and advantages if India become successful as startup india..

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY-This paper discusses about the current scenario of START-UP INDIA scheme and It also strives to describe the focuses on the impact of START UP on our economy, Challenges and opportunities of it. Government has started this scheme with the view of sustainable development and rapid economic growth and with the dream of making India a self reliant country worldwide.

***RESEARCH METHODOLOGY**

This is a descriptive research and based on secondary data. The study is basically conceptual in nature and for the purpose of the study; an extensive review of literature has been studied and identified the critical challenges facing in India.The data has been collected

from internet, related texts like textbooks, journals and other publications of professional were also consulted, news paper, websites and different reports given by the government.

DEFINITION OF A STARTUP:-This really is the most fundamental question that comes up. When such policies are announced for startups, it is important to know who would even fall within that definition. None of our present statutes define 'startups' and therefore, it was important that the government came up with a definition that was broad enough to avoid disappointments. The action plan defines startups as: "Startup means an entity, incorporated or registered in India not prior to five years, with annual turnover not exceeding INR 25 crore in any preceding financial year, working towards innovation, development, deployment or commercialisation of new products, processes or services driven by technology or intellectual property. Provided that such entity is not formed by splitting up, or reconstruction, or a business already in existence. Provided also that an entity shall cease to be a Startup if its turnover for the previous financial years has exceeded INR 25 crore or it has completed 5 years from the date of incorporation/registration. Provided further that a Startup shall be eligible for tax benefits only after it has obtained certification from the Inter-Ministerial Board, setup for such purposes."

***OBJECTIVES OF STARTUP SCHEME:**

1. Startup India campaign is based on an action plan vision.
2. Promoting bank financing for start-up ventures to boost entrepreneurship
3. Encouraging startups with jobs creation.
4. To restrict role of States in policy domain and to get rid of "license raj" and hindrances like in land permissions, foreign investment proposal, environmental clearances.
5. Promoting entrepreneurship among SCs/STs, women communities.
6. To make the young job creators rather than job seekers.
7. Promoting the scope of development of E-Commerce, e-marketing.

It was organized by Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP). A startup is an entity that is headquartered in India which was opened less than five years ago and have an annual turnover less than 25 Crore (US\$3.7 million). The government has already launched PMMY, the MUDRA Bank, a new institution set up for development and refinancing activities relating to micro units with a refinance Fund of 200 billion (US\$3.0 billion). The event was inaugurated on 16 January 2016 by the finance minister Arun Jaitley. Among the attendees were around 40 top CEOs and

startup founders and investors. The Ministry of Human Resource Development and the Department of Science and Technology have agreed to partner in an initiative to set up over 75 such startup support hubs in the National Institutes of Technology (NITs), the Indian Institutes of Information Technology (IIITs), the Indian Institutes of Science Education and Research (IISERs) and National Institutes of Pharmaceutical Education and Research (NIPERs).

The Reserve Bank of India said it will take steps to help improve the 'ease of doing businesses in the country and contribute to an ecosystem that is conducive for the growth of startup businesses.

Soft Bank, which headquarter in Japan, has invested US\$2 billion into Indian startups. The Japanese firm had pledged the total investments at US\$10 billion. Google declared to launch a startup, based on the highest votes in which the top three startups will be allowed to join the next Google Launch pad Week, and the final winner could win an amount of US\$100,000 in Google cloud credits, Oracle on 12 February 2016 announced to set up nine incubation centers in Bengaluru, Chennai, Gurgaon, Hyderabad, Mumbai, Noida, Pune, Trivandrum and Vijayawada

***EIGHT CHALLENGES FACED BY AN INDIAN**

STARTUP: Coming up with a startup idea is a very regular thing for someone aiming for an independent work life. But implementing the idea is a real big challenge which gradually gives rise to a chain of challenges. Here follows a list of challenges every startup is bound to face:-

1. Team: The most important element of every startup is a team of dedicated people who know their work and do it without being reminded of the same. Finding a good team is the first major challenge. As per a survey, 23% of the failed startups had the wrong team. Steve Hogan, who runs a company called Tech-Rx, which is a startup turn-around shop pointed out that the top reason of a failed startup is the absence of co-founders. According to Cassandra Phillips who is the founder of Falcon (a conference where founders of failed startups would share their learned lessons) "It's either you started making a startup with friends who didn't have complementary skills or the opposite - people you think have the perfect balance of skills, but then completely different ways of communicating."

2. Location: The most important problem faced by an Indian startup is the location from where it is being launched. India is a place of varied culture and taste, thus, every product might not be welcomed equally by every region. A survey found out that 42% of the failed startups attribute their failure to the lack of their market

need. Now, this is where we shouldn't follow Steve Jobs' suggestion of 'not asking what the customer wants.'

3. Marketing Strategy: This follows the above challenge. Just like the fact that every product is not meant for every location, every marketing strategy wouldn't work for every region. Poor marketing is the reason behind 14% of the failed startups.

4. Legal Constraints: Once a company has been founded, it's significant for the members to get acquainted with all the legal constraints associated with the product(s) they are dealing with. 8% of the failed startups are due to legal challenges.

5. Funding: This challenge is solely dependent on the business model. The model decides whether a huge amount of funding requires or not and most importantly when's the right time to invest.

6. Management of resources right from the beginning: Once the business starts flourishing, it gets all the more important to manage the inflow, investment in an organized way as there would soon be generated too many data to handle. Every small bit of mismanagement would amplify as the company would grow and things can get real messy and out of proportion.

7. Getting the right information/advice: This comes down to the challenge of getting in contact with the right kind of people who has in-depth knowledge on the areas concerning the startup.

8. Fighting de-motivation: This gets more important when it comes to Indian startups because in many regions here the idea of students choosing an unconventional path is still perceived as destroying one's career.

CHALLENGES CAN BE CLASSIFIED AS:

Culture - Entrepreneurship and startups are only a recent phenomenon in the country. It is only in the last decade and half that people in the country have moved from being job seekers to job creators. Doing a startup is tough and every country sees more failures than success. More often than not an entrepreneur needs to be prepared to face failures and unprecedented hardship. However, culturally we are not groomed to fail and failure is frowned upon. Entrepreneurship thrives on celebrations and a society that fails to appreciate business failures stifles innovation and creativity even before it can start. A startup failing has to be OK as failures often teach an entrepreneur, what to do and what not to do.

Mentoring - Doing a startup is perilous and often a lonely journey. You may have co-founders, but you may not necessarily possess the business acumen to succeed. Having a brilliant idea is different from making that idea a business success. For a startup, it is very important to have mentors who have been through a similar process of starting or have business experience. A great mentor is often what separates success from failure by providing

valuable inputs. However, there is no formal mechanism to mentor startups in the country. Every mentoring that happens is on an ad-hoc basis. A startup that has raised funds can count the investors for some form of mentoring, but honest, unbiased, good business mentors are far and few in between. For startups finding a good mentor is often an uphill task.

Policies - Government is the single largest enabler for the entrepreneurial ecosystem. Government's role in ease of doing business and helping companies start is vital to ensuring success. The latest World Bank Ease of Doing Business (out of 189 economies) ranks India at an abysmal 142 where starting a business rank for the country is even lower at 158. It is uncannily difficult to start a business in India and myriad laws and regulations means it takes about 30 days to comply compared to just 9 days in OECD countries. The government's role has so far been limited to giving out grants and loans, but without an effective, enabling environment, implementation is far off the target. In this regard it will be interesting to see the contours of the recently announced Startup Fund in this year's budget. For startups to thrive and succeed, the government has a lot to do and understand the importance of entrepreneurship in economic development.

Hiring - The economy has been in a flux and along with the world economy the heady days of high growth are long gone. In an uncertain economy where one is not sure about demand, for a startup, it is particularly difficult to make correct estimates on the number of employees needed. This, however, is the minor problem where the biggest issue is about finding skilled manpower. India's skilling need is so huge that National Skill Development Corporation (NSDC) has been mandated to skill 150 million Indians by 2022. For a startup, it is particularly difficult to attract and hire talent and skilled workers. A startup often cannot match the salaries drawn at larger companies nor is a job at a startup seen as a steady one. This means startups face severe hiring challenges and at times have to settle for the next best option.

Funding - Capital and access to capital has been a perennial problem for startups. While, of late angel investors, venture capital and private equity have brought succor to some extent, a large number of startups still grapple to raise funds from institutional setup. Funding challenge is not merely limited to seed rounds, but also for vital Series A and B rounds. For a startup looking to scale, it is still very hard to raise rounds to scale as the number of investors that write larger cheques in India are very limited in number.

KEY POINTS TO FACE THE CHALLENGES:

Single Window Clearance even with the help of a mobile application. 10,000 crore fund of funds. 80%

reduction in patent registration fee.
 Modified and more friendly Bankruptcy Code to ensure 90-day exit window.
 Freedom from mystifying inspections for 3 years.
 Freedom from Capital Gain Tax for 3 years.
 Freedom from tax in profits for 3 years.
 Eliminating red tape.

Self-certification compliance.

Innovation hub under Atal Innovation Mission.

Starting with 5 lakh schools to target 10 lakh children for innovation programme.

New schemes to provide IPR protection to start-ups and new firms.

Encourage entrepreneurship.

Stand India across the world as a start-up hub.

OPPORTUNITIES REGARDING STARTUPS:

The Indian Middle Class Rises- The success of an economy depends on a number of social, economic, political conditions prevalent in the country. India got its independence in 1947 and thus started the difficult nation building process. The government of the day focused on making quality education available to India. Getting good education and hard work remained the mantra for the large Indian middle class population, something that you see deeply ingrained in this segment even today.

The Indian middle class story saw a huge shift in early 1990 with the introduction of reforms and the increasing integration of Indian economy into the global market. The economic reforms coupled with globalization saw a huge mind shift among the Indian middle class. The rise of Indian IT Industry in the late 90s not only gave rise to an increase in average income levels in the country but also created a well-traveled global Indian. The increase in average income created a sense of financial security in the minds of Indians who could now think beyond basic needs of **roti kapda and makan**.

Thus was created a new breed of the Indian middle class – very well educated, hardworking and ambitious. Someone with a global mindset and awareness about the problems that exist in our country and how technology had solved these problems in the west. Today as the environment becomes more and more conducive to start your own venture, it is this breed of the new middle class Indian who is creating global companies out of India. The nascent and unorganized state of infrastructure within various segment of the Indian industry and the opportunity presented by India's population makes each and every sector in India very attractive right now. Entrepreneurs in India have identified these opportunities and are trying to digitize/ organize various sectors. There is an evident change in the professional and social preferences of the new Indian population.

2-Changing Job Preferences- While the silicon valley

gave us new gods, the likes of Steve Jobs and Mark Zuckerbergs, who showed us how following your heart was the best thing that you can do to yourself, the new age middle class Indian, with an increased risk appetite is surely walking on that path !The new age India today is ready to break away from the typical career paths, to take a chance, to follow their hearts and this is clearly evident from the hiring trends that we are currently seeing in the country. Traditional recruiters in India are said to be under pressure to up their game as more and more talent is tending towards working with growth companies. A budding startup ecosystem, challenging assignments, huge funding and an associated coolness quotient are attracting a lot of talent towards the Indian startup space.

3- Trends in Graduate Hiring- Hiring in Indian IITs always makes news due to the crore plus packages that are offered to the students. Hiring trends in IITs are also seen as showcasing the trends of interests that young talented India is portraying. And the trends in first phase of the IIT placement season that concluded on December 31, 2014 were clearly showing a growing interest towards startups. The year not only saw more number of startups actively participating in the campus recruitment process but also saw them offering higher packages in order to compete with our regular visitors and lure the students. In fact, startups and ecommerce companies were among the topmost recruiters of the year. Placements in start-ups have accounted for 13% of the total number of students placed from IIT-Madras where as many as 65 start-ups recruited and made 122 offers in more than 75 profiles.

The year also saw a number of IIT students either declining job offers or completely skipping the campus recruitment process itself, mostly, due to their growing interest into entrepreneurship. As per reports, at least 40 students across IITs have opted out of campus placement process to start their own ventures. While in the last placement season, only 1 student from IIT-Bombay opted out of the process for entrepreneurial pursuit in 2014, this year the number went up to 11. The number of students at IIT-Kanpur shunning the process for their startups in 2014 placement season was reported to be 5, which was at 14 this season. At IIT- Guwahati, 6 students opted out of the process to pursue entrepreneurship in the 2015 season. The number had stood at 3 last year. Unlike few years back when IITians preferred to get job experience in the industry before launching their own start-ups, many IIT fresher's now prefer to pursue their dreams, experiment and come up with innovative products & services via their own startups immediately after graduating from college.

4-MBA Hiring Trends- Hiring trend among top MBA

colleges also make a news every year because of the high packages and also because it is a reflection of preferences of India. Among India's top MBA colleges too students are lining up to get placed in the startup and e-commerce sectors making it one of the hottest job segments in India right now. According to an ET survey, the number of students opting for jobs in startups and e-commerce companies grew from 1 in 9 from the 2013-2015 batches from 1 in 19 from 2012-2014 batches. Startups and e-commerce sectors are offering salaries up to 10-18 lakhs. A number of analysts are comparing this trend in hiring to that of initial times of the Indian IT Industry.

5-Mid and Senior Management Turns To Startups- The opportunity and challenges that startups and growth companies are providing today is really huge. Talk to any mid or senior management executive in India today and you cannot miss hearing about how they are looking for something challenging to work on. A lot of mid/ senior level managers who could not take a risk early in life due to responsibilities feel much more comfortable about it today after having made a considerable amount of savings and looking at the support that the startup ecosystem in India is seeing. Increasingly a trend is being observed where more and more mid-level officials are quitting cushy and humdrum jobs at big firms to work for startups. Startups are not only offering challenging assignments but with lot of funding happening in the space are also able to provide with huge compensation packages including stakes and equity in start-ups, or milestone-linked compensation packages making startups a very attractive value proposition for people looking for additional challenges. The risk associated with whether the startup succeed or fails always remains but with good packages and a lot of challenging opportunities available to people who have proven themselves in the startup environment, more and more people are ready to take the leap.

6- Changing Social Outlook- There was a time in India many years ago when the only socially accepted job was a government job. Then came the private sector jobs, then the MNCs and slowly and steadily jobs at startups and having your own startup are also gaining more and more social acceptance each day. In the middle of a number of reports which said how having your own startup is not very conducive to your marriage prospects, Jeevansathi, a matrimonial website has witnessed a 55 % increase in self-employed profiles in last couple of years. Rohan Mathur, the VP and head of Jeevansathi said that nowadays parents are fine with an entrepreneur groom as long as he has good educational background. The number of couples who have started companies together is also growing in India, thus showcasing a trend that more and more families are becoming open to taking some risks.

RECOMMENDATIONS- But there are some issues which have to be considered before implementing this

program: Indian banks have already such a huge NPA. Considering the success rates of the start ups, Indian banks are taking a huge risks with their money. Finance is just a fraction of issues the entrepreneurs are facing. There are a lot of issues such as infrastructure, a platform to discuss their issues among different entrepreneurs and experts, and finding markets for their products. Only with financial support an entrepreneurial venture cannot become successful. Issues like red-tapism and licence raj are not yet sorted out. "Ease of business doing in India" is still an issue. The money obtained from banks may be channeled for the wrong purposes. So instead of giving an whole sum of money as credit, it should be taken care that money be transferred in steps on basis of an evaluation by an expert committee.

CONCLUSION- To conclude, the action plan is largely optimistic since it shows a very positive intent by the government. However, going forward, it is critical that the government sets up a team of founders, investors, angels, lawyers and accountants who can ensure that the final policies surrounding startups are as flawless as possible and maintain the right balance between accountability, transparency and doing business. Overall "Startup India" is a good programme which can revolutionize Indian economy and even may result in an "Indian Google" or "Indian apple". But care must be taken that the above lacunae are also taken for consideration.

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